

THE SPECIFICITY OF THE INTERNET SLANG IMPLEMENTATION IN THE PROCESS OF COMMUNICATION IN CHAT ROOMS

The article is devoted to the analysis of the Internet slang as a key aspect of interaction in chat rooms. The author highlights the specificity of slang in the process of communication in chat rooms. The article is based on the chats of modern social networks. The work examines the definite units of the Internet slang, such as: acronyms, abbreviations, shortened words and jargon. The author puts a stress on the actuality of a work due to the speed development of chatspeak communication, which is endless source of slang, and its narrow exploring. The article's goals are to set the main principles of the Internet slang forming and to describe its key features which will serve as a basic for future works. It highlights the specificity of the Internet slang usage and underlines the importance of its analysis due to the growing interest in the lexical, grammatical, phonetical, semantic and other aspects of the Internet communication whether it is interaction between the youth or the adults. The author sets main principles of slang forming and examines this phenomenon using the examples from two languages – English and Ukrainian. Moreover, the article presents issues which are turned to the comparison of the features of the Internet slang forming.

Key words: Internet slang, communication, chat room, social networks, interaction, acronym, abbreviation, shortened words, jargon.

Заболнова М.В. Особливості реалізації мережевого сленгу в процесі комунікації в інтернет чатах. *Стаття присвячена дослідженню мережевого сленгу як ключового аспекту взаємодії в інтернет чатах. Автор висвітлює особливості сленгу в процесі спілкування в чатах. Стаття бере за основу чати сучасних соціальних мереж. Робота розглядає окремі складові мережевого сленгу – акроніми, абрєвіатури, скорочення та жаргон. Автор наголошує, що актуальність роботи полягає у швидкому розвитку мережевих чатів, які є джерелом сленгізмів, та їх малодослідженості. Стаття ставить за мету виокремити основні принципи утворення сленгу та скомпонувати його особливості, які стануть основою майбутніх робіт.*

Ключові слова: мережевий сленг, комунікація, інтернет чат, соціальні мережі, акронім, абрєвіатура, скорочення, жаргон.

Заболнова М.В. Особенности реализации сетевого сленга в процессе коммуникации в интернет чатах. *Статья посвящается исследованию сетевого сленга, как ключевого аспекта взаимодействия в интернет чатах. Автор показывает особенности сленга в процессе общения в чатах. Статья основывается на чатах современных социальных сетей. Работа рассматривает отдельные составляющие сетевого сленга – акронимы, абрєвиатуры, сокращения и жаргонизмы. Автор делает ударение на том, что актуальность работы лежит в быстром развитии сетевых чатов, которые являются источником сленгизмов, и их ограниченном исследовании. Статья ставит за цель выделить основные принципы образования сленга и скомпонировать его особенности, которые станут ключевыми для будущих работ.*

Ключевые слова: сетевой сленг, коммуникация, интернет чат, социальные сети, акроним, абрєвиатура, сокращение, жаргон.

Communication has entered all the levels of life whether you are a lecturer or a student. The last decade provides the world with numerous works devoted to the analysis of speaking specificity which includes phonetics, lexicology, pragmatics and many other aspects of language building. There are many works which are devoted to the analysis of slang among which are the papers of Crystal D., Stryga E.V., Zaitzeva S.V., Zavodna L. [6; 4; 2; 1]. Nowadays communication serves as a key to everything – decision making, interior politics and various problems which are to be solved with the help of negotiations. But modern types of communication are even broader and for the last decade they have been binding themselves with the Internet. Trendy social networks have already reached every home and position; they do not simply provide people with news and details from the personal life they can work as a source of interaction which obviously includes communication in formal as well as informal styles.

Our work mainly based on informal communication which is widely presented in chat rooms and includes the phenomenon such as the Internet slang. The actuality of this work is in the speed development of social networks, which are the main source of the Internet slang, and its narrow exploring. The goals are to set the main principles of the Internet slang forming and to describe its key features which will serve as a basic for future works.

Nevertheless, the researches turned to the analysis of communication are widely spread but do not contain the whole picture of the situation. First of all, it is necessary to decide which communicative groups are to be included into the chat-speak. Nowadays we can interact with other people with the help of various social networks which include Facebook, Twitter, Telegram, WhatsApp, etc. as well as e-mails. The main difference between those two groups are the time required for answering. If we take the first group (social networks), we may have live immediate chat which can fully substitute the face to face communication when e-mails serve more to exchange important files, documents, they have bigger load capacity and no moderator that makes your conversation private. This work will deal with the first group which is turned to simple interaction and which uses slang to ease the communication. Thus, it is quite important to figure out what the concept “slang” means. According to the linguist Kochergan M. “Slang are the words which are suitable for the communicative language of people who are connected with the definite similarity of interests” [3; P. 215], so, our work is based on this definition.

The main question is: “Why do we need slang?” – many will answer: “To make the conversation easier” or “To save speech efforts”. But the British lexicographer Eric Partridge proposed in his book “Slang today and yesterday” not less than fifteen different reasons of using slang, they are: “in playfulness or waggishness, as an exercise either in wit and ingenuity or in humour, to be ‘different’, to be picturesque, to be unmistakably arresting, even startling, to escape from clichés, or to be brief and concise, to enrich the language. to lend an air of solidity, concreteness, to the abstract, to soften the tragedy, to speak or write down to an inferior, for ease of social intercourse, to induce either friendliness or intimacy of a deep or a durable kind, to show that one belongs to a certain school, trade, or profession, artistic or intellectual set, or social class; in brief, to be ‘in the swim’ or to establish contact, to

show or prove that someone is not ‘in the swim’, to be secret” [8]. The most current and useful reasons for the Internet users today are, probably, playfulness, the desire to be different and to be brief; these three features show the main rulers of the Internet slang development. If we take a closer look at the life round us it will become understandable that people spend more time communicating via the Internet thus it has already formed its own language which cannot exist anymore without slang.

The picture we have today is the following – acronyms, abbreviations, shortened words and jargon – they all serve as tools for forming modern Internet slang. Firstly, we will work out the main principles of acronyms and abbreviations. It is important to understand that every acronym is an abbreviation when not every abbreviation can be an acronym. So, according to Cambridge Dictionary “abbreviation” is a short form of a word or phrase and “acronym” is an abbreviation consisting of the first letters of each word in the name of something, pronounced as a word [5]. So, *NATO* is both abbreviation and acronym when *USA* is abbreviation but not an acronym due to the pronouncing form. Acronyms and abbreviations, which occupy the biggest area in the modern users’ communication, appear in every sphere of life. *LOL* (Laugh Out Loud), *OMG* (Oh My God), *TGIF* (Thanks God It is Friday), *WTH* (What’s the Hell), *PhD* (Doctor of Philosophy) and etc. Mostly they are formed with the help of the first letters of the words given in the phrase but as well some are formed basing on the phonetics – *CU* (See You), *CUS* (See You Soon) and others. Moreover, the English Internet slang includes acronyms and abbreviations with the Latin origin – *i.e.* that comes from *id est* and means “it is”, “namely”, “which is”, *etc* comes from *et cetera* and means “so on”, “and other”, *e.g.* comes from *exempli gratiā* and means “for example”, “for instance”. Talking about the Ukrainian language we can see another tendency of the Internet slang development – the origins of the words may have three roots – Ukrainian, English and Russian as well; that can be explained with the fact that the Ukrainian Internet slang has started its development not longer than four years ago due to the high spreading of nationalization in the light of the situation on the East of the country. There are many acronyms and abbreviations which originate from the English language – *лвл* which comes from “level”, *ни* which comes from “no problems” and many others, it is also important to point out that these abbreviations have the same meaning with the words from the source language. Also there are some abbreviations with Russian origin for instance *снк* which comes from the word “спасибо” but the rapid development of the Ukrainian-speaking system of abbreviations we have *дяк.* which comes from the similar Ukrainian meaning “дякую”, the next one is *НМСД* which comes from “На Мою Скромну Думку” and this as well as many other units has a full equivalent in the English language *IMHO* “In My Humble Opinion” as well this abbreviation has the English sounding form in the target language “*IMXO*” which is widely used in chat rooms. Also there are abbreviations with the Ukrainian origin only – *тчн* which comes from “точно” and means “exactly”, *хз* which comes from “хто знає” and means “who knows”, etc. Though, the Internet slang of the English language which may be implemented with the help of acronyms and abbreviations are composed basing on the words of two definite languages – the English and Latin ones, when the Ukrainian Internet slang, which is quite young

and only makes the first steps on the Internet area, are formed on the basis of the Ukrainian, English and Russian words. But nowadays the wide area of the Internet communication has more tools of slang implementation – they include shortened words, jargon and many other language phenomena. It is important to stress out that the shortened words may also be distinguished as acronyms and abbreviations due to the way of their forming but in this work they will take a separate place to show a different principle of their using. The shortened words are formed with the help of leaving only one or two syllables of the original word for instance *lab* – *laboratory*, *ad* – *advertisement*, *bye* is also a kind of shortening which comes from a phrase “good bye”. The trendy Internet slang sets such “word building” on another stage. In both languages this kind of shortening is possible and widely used. *Див* which comes from “дивись” and means “look” or “see” depending on a context, *бл* – “близько” which means “near”, *през* – “президент” which means “the President”, *комп* – “комп’ютер” with meaning “computer” and many others. Such kind of communication is acceptable and useful due to the principle of speech saving efforts and it makes the process of interaction in chat rooms easier. However, people all over the world continue developing the Internet Slang because of spreading needs of the users to be brief and understandable for co-speakers.

Another phenomenon of the Internet slang is jargon. It can be met everywhere; the Internet is one of the tens of places where jargon is used. According to the Cambridge dictionary jargon is a special word or phrase that is used by particular groups of people, especially in their work [5]. Whether jargon is professional or gender it still serves to underline the specificity of one separate speaking group and its context (in our work – users’ group) but the main point is that the Internet may also contain professional and gender classifications. Jargons are tightly connected with a context and mostly are not understandable outside it or outside the group itself but still some words may get out of the group and become an independent word used by the people throughout the Internet. The English as the first and the most used language on the Internet has made a wonderful thing – it may transform its Internet slang into the independent and international words, mainly it happens to the “computer jargon” such as: *troll* or *trolling* which describe a person or a process of leaving an intentionally annoying message on the internet, in order to get attention or cause trouble [5], but as well there are words common only for the English-speaking users, such as *lurker* which means a person who reads the messages in a chat room without taking part [5]. The Ukrainian language provides the users with some jargons which have already entered the everyday life – *аська* which describes the chatspeak on “ICQ” (I Seek You), *залізо* which literally means “iron” and is used describing computer hardware, *апгрейдити* which originates from the English word “upgrade” and refers to the process of modernization of the computer (not only) software, *глючити* “bugging” this word refers to the incorrect work of devices, *віндузятники* [7] which describes people who prefer using Windows, etc. So, as far as the Internet slang grows fast, soon it will, probably, become an independent language with its own rules and obligations.

To sum up it is important to underline that every type of communication may become a separate system of interaction – the communication in the chat rooms

is not an exception. Nowadays the concept “communication” is quite broader and its fundamental functions are implemented in different ways. The communication via the Internet has become inseparable way of users’ interaction – the co-speakers develop the live language and produce a big amount of forms of brief answers and questions putting the speech saving efforts on the first place. The key aspects of the Internet slang implementation still are acronyms, abbreviations, shortened words and jargon as well. As we can see the Internet slang of one language may have roots in other languages due to the influence which is done over it in numerous international chat rooms. As any other sphere of living – communication will not stop its development and will continue producing new ways of interaction.

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